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Growth of Youth-Owned Micro and Small Enterprises in Kigali City, Rwanda: What is the Role of Government Entrepreneurial Interventions?

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Abstract

Micro and Small Enterprises are major players in the wealth of nations, and therefore various entrepreneurial interventions were launched for boosting the economies and standards of living by creating employment opportunities and profits. However, these MSEs have experienced some problems which lessen their growth. The objective of the research was to investigate the effect of government interventions on the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Kigali City, Rwanda. The study was anchored on the resource-based view, Gibb's support theory, adoption theory, and growth of a firm theory/ Explanatory and descriptive research designs were adopted. The sample was 154 respondents drawn from three districts of Kigali city with a population of 252 youth-owned MSEs. Data was collected using a questionnaire and analyzed using multiple linear regression analysis. The study concludes that entrepreneurial training, access to credit, technology-based online social media, and market access effectively influenced the growth of MSEs in Kigali City, Rwanda. The study recommended that government entrepreneurial interventions should be effectively factored into policy-making and program implementation for sufficient growth of MSEs. MSEs should adopt technology-based online social media to market their products to the global market beyond the Rwanda boundary. Moreover it's an effective management tool for customer relations for online business.

Keywords: Government Entrepreneurial Interventions, Growth of Youth Owned MSEs, Resource Based Review, Rwanda

1. Introduction

The contribution of Micro and Small Enterprises (MSEs) to the wealth of a nation has been acknowledged by several governments (Muathe, 2010, Chen & Yuan, 2021). In this modern business world, MSEs are proven as an effective instrument since it reduces socio-economic issues related to poverty, income inequality, and unemployment, especially among people aged between 18-35 years, (Muathe, Wawire, & Ofafa, 2013, Tundui & Tundui, 2013). Therefore, MSEs deserved to get entrepreneurial interventions attributable to their outstanding pertinence in ensuring a perpetual upturn in per-capita income, output, and employment opportunities, (Tekele,

2019). Different authors argue that MSEs are at different phases of growth as the extent of entrepreneurial interventions given to the MSE sector differs from one sector to another, nation to nation, and or developed to growing countries. As such government entrepreneurial interventions were increased in which the growth of youth-owned MSEs would be augmented, (World Bank, 2014).

Various scholars avowed that there was an increase in the number of MSEs and their growth caused by an increase in government entrepreneurial interventions in many countries of the world. Thus, nowadays more than 78% of all enterprises operating their businesses are in the MSE sector across the world, (Muathe, & Muraguri-Makau, 2020, Khan & Khalique, 2014). It has been noted in different research that MSEs contribute about 20% to the GDP and 35% of total workers are engaged in this sector worldwide, (World Bank, 2014). Furthermore, micro-enterprises recruit between 1 and 9 workers whereas small enterprises hire between 10 and 49 workers across the world. It has been demonstrated that in 2012, Malaysian MSEs contributes greater than 50% of the GDP, (Byrnes, *et al*, 2015). They also hired 3 million workers; corresponding to 65.1% of the total employment. This sector is the principal pillar of Singapore's economy where MSEs provide 62% of employment and contributes around 47% to the country's GDP (UNCTAD, 2016). According to Jirabi (2017), in countries of EAC, MSEs account for more than 90% of all private businesses, and they absorb more than 24% of the country's GDP.

In a growing country like Rwanda, the contribution of MSEs induced policymakers to concert efforts for improving the business environment in that MSEs are operating and their business growth, (World Bank, 2014). Consequently, MSEs are crucial accelerators of social and economic development and wealth formation due to their substantial contributions to the national economy. Government entrepreneurial interventions enabled MSEs to increase growth in the manner of accessing knowledge-based resources and physical assets such as buildings, lands, equipment, machines, and adoption of suitable technology which facilitates a firm to interact with customers, and stay competitive, (Aidara *et al*, 2021). The Rwandan MSEs have been speeding up's vision of 2050 by building robust government entrepreneurial interventions (World Bank, 2014). This sector contributes to the country's economy by uplifting public revenue and creating more employment opportunities, (Okello, 2014).

Despite these efforts made by the government to expand the output of MSEs, the growth is still scanty (Aidara *et al*, 2021). They encounter problems of restricted financial capital and skills, quickly changing customer needs that require a dynamic market orientation, and constant technological innovations which are critical to firms' growth (Irungu & Kamau, 2015). As remarked by Gallup (2014), these challenges negatively affect 40% of new businesses failing during the first five years of operation. Overcoming these challenges requires strong entrepreneurial interventions to improve the growth of MSEs. It has been noted that public entrepreneurial interventions could have a positive impact on the growth if the specific interventions provided to this sector are adequate in nature, extent, and quality; e.g: quality of training, the extent of credits, level and nature of technology adopted and ability to operate profitably in markets, which is dominated by large firms, (Gherghina *et al*, 2020).

This study contributes to the study knowledge by considering the effects of four aspects of government entrepreneurial interventions. Many studies focused on one or two factors when carrying out research. They also considered RBV theory and Gibb's MSEs support theory only. This study also contributes to the research by providing four theories that support the study's hypotheses. The primary theory, RBV theory, describes all kinds of resources allowing firms to achieve full growth. Gibb's support theory demonstrates software and hardware support helps MSEs to realize their growth and supports the RBV theory. It also enlightens how the MSEs respond to all types of support. Adoption theory demonstrates the steps that firms follow in accepting or rejecting new technology. Finally, the theory of the growth of a firm gives details of all resources needed for firm growth.

It is for this reason that government has to induce entrepreneurial interventions which are significant strategies for improving the growth of youth-owned MSEs. Therefore, the study endeavored to investigate the contribution of entrepreneurial training, credit access, and technology-based social media and market access to the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda.

1.1 Statement of the problem

Micro and Small Enterprises globally play a very important role in contributing to the Rwandan economy through employment generation and its significant contributions to the GDP, (World Bank, 2014). Therefore, entrepreneurial interventions have been initiated by various governments because they are widely seen as one of the essential factors that expand enterprises' development through profits and job generation (Rwamigabo, 2019). Even though the efforts made by the governments toward entrepreneurial interventions, the growth of enterprises is still unsatisfying (Uwitonze, 2016).

Past studies by Abay, Temanu, and Gebreegziabher, (2015) and Rwamigabo (2019) advanced four aspects that can influence the growth of MSEs specifically: entrepreneurial training, credit access, technology adoption, and market access. However, most of the previous studies concentrated on one or two aspects when carrying out research. The current study employed four factors to seek the direct relationship between government entrepreneurial interventions and the growth of Micro and Small Enterprises.

Different empirical studies averred that public entrepreneurial interventions have a positive influence on the firms' growth in the manner of accessing available resources, (Jibrilla, 2013; Simiyu 2018). This resource accessibility leads the firms to more opportunities for growth. The studies confirmed that interventions in entrepreneurship should have structures that allow MSEs to get existing resources required for firm growth. The studies assumed that there is a direct relationship between government entrepreneurial interventions and the firm's growth. The paper, therefore, seeks to illustrate the link between government entrepreneurial interventions and the growth of MSEs.

1.2 Objectives of the Study

The objective of the study was to investigate the effect of Government Interventions on the Growth of Youth-Owned MSEs in Kigali City, Rwanda

2. Review of Literature

This section revises the conceptual, theoretical, and empirical literature related to the research objectives.

2.1. Theoretical review

The research is anchored on four theories namely: Resource-Based View, adoption theory, Gibb's support theory, and growth theory of a firm.

2.1.1 Resource-Based Theory

The proponent of the Resource-Based View theory was Penrose (1959) who put forward that resource accessibility leads to the firm's growth. Alvarez and Busenitz, (2001) supported the theory by confirming that the growth of any business organization can be achieved when a firm holds the resources that others cannot get. An enterprise can achieve long-run growth if the resources held are characterized by uniqueness, scarcity, and inimitability, or hard to copy means that resources cannot be copied by other rivals, (Thompson, 2004). This facilitates enterprise to create unique values for clients and expansion achievement. Barney (1991) demonstrates six types of resources that enable a firm to realize growth and become competitive. For example financial, tangible, technological, organizational capital, intellectual and human resources. According to Aldrich, (1999), all these resources have been categorized into three classes which are financial, social, and human.

The theory provides two categories of resources to be accessed by an enterprise and these resources can be either material or non-material, (Jones and Hill, 2009). Tangible resources are visible and concrete; namely: land, buildings, and equipment while non-materials resources are palpable and computable. For example trademarks, administration processes, and routines of organizations that the firm used to organize and interrelate these resources, the reputation of a firm; goodwill, and among others. The theory states that resources used by a firm to interact with clients and competitors are external intangible resources, (Simeh, 2011). The maximum utilization

of resources is important for the business organization to achieve its objective, (According to Jones & Hill, (2009). The theory also reveals the hat business sector should not be overlooked since it plays a vital role in determining enterprises' growth and therefore entrepreneurs must consider the sector for deciding activities to be carried out. The RBV was utilized because it is anchored on four components of government entrepreneurial interventions which are the main factors affecting the growth of firms.

2.1.2 Gibb's MSEs Support Theory

The proponent of the Gibb model was Gibb (1998) and the author explains different support services that government policymakers must emphasize on them when designing entrepreneurial interventions for firms' growth. The model describes two kinds of support needed by the enterprise sector to realize its growth such as non-material and material support. The non-material support is training, counseling, consultancy, and others while material support comprises credit platform, infrastructure, and materials. The theory elucidates policy or interventions must be flexible, it means that support services can change resulting from a change in the needs of enterprises; a change in support structure; a change in institutional structure for firms, and a change in policy for the development of firms. Gibb states that there should be a policy structure clarifying supportive action to boost the firm growth and key aspects to measure achievable enterprises' growth. The theory notes that support structure should specify features. It has been asserted that MSEs' needs should not be overlooked from the beginning of program planning when programs are based on the need of enterprises; it reduces the probability of its failure.

The theory stipulates that the institutional framework should outline features and types of entrepreneurial interventions and explains how MSEs can benefit from initiated programs or policies. It should indicate institutions in charge of MSEs and their capability to capacitate enterprises for achieving their full growth. Gibb's theory has a role in determining how entrepreneurial intervention can change as a result of the alteration in the needs of the MSEs, reform in the support structure, change in institutions structure for MSEs, and change in policy for the development of the MSE sector. However, training, access to credit, market information, and technology infrastructure are essential supports that can be used to improve the growth of enterprises.

2.1.3 Adoption Theory

The proponents of adoption theory were Ryan and Gross (1943) and it is built on the assumption that individuals can adopt new technology by imitable character, (Hamed, 2017). The background and understanding of people are key elements that encourage the utilization of technology in society. Dearing and Jeffrey (2018) explains that people can learn new knowledge about technology-based online social media via their cultures. It has been stated that technology can also be learned through training, shared beliefs, or practices among enterprises. Innovation diffusion has a vital role in influencing an individual's adoption decision.

The technology-based online social media has been described as a particular social system that businesspeople are currently using to communicate with their business partners and competitors and it can be learned through culture over time. Rogers (1962) developed the adoption theory by demonstrating the stages that individuals have to follow when making a particular innovation acceptance, or rejection. The adopters must learn knowledge of how to apply the new technology and adopters must know the value of online social media before making an acceptance or rejection decisions, ((Tuten & Marks, 2012). Olupot and Mayoka (2013) noted three reasons that can guide an enterprise in accepting or rejecting new technology. These are rivals' forces, low awareness of firms, and benefits expected from new technology-based online social media. According to Ardjouman (2014), different enterprises use technology as an influence resulting from trading partners, rivals, and government support and policy.

The business conditions and enterprise features are the main aspects that determine the utilization of technology in the enterprise. The theory also notes that technology acquisition depends on how an enterprise inspires its employees to adopt changes that are brought along with embracing technology. The theory brings out the importance of technological innovation adoption that an enterprise has to make for the enhancement of its capacity in handling issues related to growth (Oliveira & Martins, 2011). It also establishes all stages that a firm has to follow when making a particular online social media acceptance or rejection.

2.1.4 Theory of Growth of a Firm

The proponent of the growth of a firm theory was Penrose (1959) who enlightens the significance of resources in shaping a firm's growth. According to Evans (1987), the rule of proportionate growth avows that the growth of every business organization in the market is autonomous of its entire size. Therefore, micro, small, medium, and large enterprises have the same average proportionate rates of growth that is to say in the market; all firms can grow at the same ratio regardless of their size if they are given equal opportunity to access resources needed for growth. This theory describes the five stages of growth that all enterprises go through. The first phase is called the start-up stage and at this phase, the enterprise brings its idea into implementation.

The second stage is the survival stage whereby the firm deals with how it can make more cash flow for growth and continue its business operations in long run. The theory asserts that an enterprise is required to have enough cash flow for its survival and continued operations. The third is the success stage for which the firm increases its output and earnings through professionalization and technology adoption. The fourth phase is the take-off stage in which the enterprise tries to use gained resources at the optimum level and enhance the competencies of its employees through training. The last one is called the maturity stage whereby a firm must access and use effectively resources to attain full growth. The accessibility of resources determines how MSEs identify opportunities and convert them into profitable business ventures as well as facilitate growth. In the perspective of this study, the growth of a firm theory brings out the relevance because it shows how access to resources can be a source of competitive advantage and growth achievement.

2.2 Empirical Review

The study is attached to various constructs such as growth, government entrepreneurial interventions, individual characteristics, and micro and small enterprises. Thus, this section revised the conceptual literature which accurately explains each construct.

2.2.1 Entrepreneurial Training and Growth of Youth-Owned MSEs

Many researchers have agreed that entrepreneurial training has made notable improvements in the area of enterprise development across the world, (Mano *et al*, 2012). Therefore, various governments introduced training programs with the perception that entrepreneurial training would help to influence entrepreneurial culture and build enterprising economies among many young men and women by developing their mindsets and attitudes about enterprise management. Entrepreneurial training has been used to upturn entrepreneurial abilities with the aim focus on how to use technological innovation change, the techniques of applying modern management systems, customers' satisfaction shown by repeat purchasing, marketing strategies, and well-kept business records, (DeGobbi, 2014; Andaregie, *et al*, 2022). Entrepreneurial training substantially influences the growth of a firm if skills learned by youth entrepreneurs translated into more practical work, (Kithae, Kimani, & Mburia, 2013).

According to Kithae, Kimani, and Mburia (2013), entrepreneurial training can considerably contribute to the growth of a firm when skills learned by entrepreneurs translated into more practical work. Different empirical studies stated that trainees did not apply their gained skills because youth could not access financial resources. Yet, another study carried out by UNCTAD (2016) demonstrated that 70% of MSEs who had received training; could conveniently accomplish business undertakings. The study carried out by Salfiya and Haleem (2021) on entrepreneurial training and its contribution to enterprises' growth in Sri Lanka. The study utilized an explanatory research design and the finding asserted that training in marketing, quality maintenance, and financial management positively influences the enterprises' growth. Mohamed (2017) researched the contribution of entrepreneurial training to the growth of enterprises held by youth in Somalia. It has been noted that entrepreneurship training has a positive effect on the growth of firms. The study further affirmed that training benefited youth-owned MSEs by stimulating income in Somalia.

The Moroccan government has trained youth-owned MSEs with the purpose that they may advance their business capabilities; grow their enterprises, and endlessly contribute to the Moroccan economy, (Gray & Finley-Hervey,

2005). Umutoni (2018) observed that entrepreneurial training has enhanced the competencies and growth of MSEs in Rwanda. Entrepreneurial training has been documented as a major factor of interventions that the government provided to the MSEs for stimulating their growth. This training was normally aimed to transfer entrepreneurial capabilities which facilitate youth to carry out business activities. Thus, the study strived to provide detailed data by investigating the contribution of entrepreneurial training to the growth of youth-owned MSEs. The following hypotheses were formulated based on the conceptual framework:

Ho1: Entrepreneurial training has no significant contribution to the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Rwanda.

2.2.2 Access to Credit and Growth of Youth-Owned MSEs

Preceding studies have seen access to credit as the primary factor that can allow MSEs to access all other remaining resources (Rajan & Zingales, 2001; Ghoul, Guedhami, & Kim, 2017). Access to financial capital influences significantly the competitiveness and growth of MSEs. Owolabi, and Obida (2012) pointed out that for firms to achieve growth and be competitive, they must hold financial capital. However, Edwards *et al.*, (2021) noted that the main growth restriction remains funds. This is because the majority of youth-owned enterprises do not get credits due to the collateral security required by banks. In another study Pandya (2012) noted that several countries formed microcredit programs targeting MSEs, but the findings revealed that the majority of MSEs are not able to acquire microcredits as a result of a lack of borrowing security with higher value, (Fatoki & Asah, 2011). Microfinance and financial institutions neglected youth-owned MSEs because most of them are not able to offer financial statement documents required by banks. The bank requirements limit their access to credit and affect negatively enterprise growth. The majority of MSEs prefer to use informal sources of financing.

According to research done by Nwosu, Emmanuel, and Anthony (2016), on financial credits and the expansion of small businesses in Nigeria. It has been found that access to credit has a vital role in assisting enterprises to access all kinds of assets needed by SMEs and improve firm performance. The study asserted that Nigerian SMEs still use informal sources of financing because they are not able to access banks' credits. Ovat, (2016) noted that the full growth of MSEs is limited by the shortage or inadequate credit. Lack of access to credit negatively influences the firm growth and affects a firm's decision to invest in fixed capital, research, and development (Muchiri, Shukla, & Kibachia, 2017). Pandya (2012) proved that credit has an important influence on SMEs' growth.

Wellalage and Locke (2016) investigated financial loans and the performance of enterprises in Sub-Saharan Countries and noted that the main growth restriction remains funds. This is because youth-owned enterprises do not get credits due to the collateral security required by banks. The study found that MSEs with high rates of growth; are enterprises that used or accessed credit from loan institutions. Previous researches show that most institutions do not target youth-owned MSEs because MSEs are not able to offer financial statement documents required by banks. On contrary, Geleta and Talegeta (2019) noted that several countries formed microcredit programs targeting MSEs, but their surveys revealed that the majority of MSEs are not able to access them. This is because high numbers of MSEs are not able to access bank credits. After all, owners of enterprises are required to have borrowing security with higher value, (Fatoki & Asah, 2011). These requirements limit their access to credit and affect negatively enterprise growth.

Mpakaniye and Paul (2017) affirmed that the establishment of a youth development fund facilitates MSEs to access bank credit, particularly those without sufficient collateral required by financial institutions. Most of the empirical studies confirmed that credit accessibility was also assisting MSEs in contributing to the country's development. The Rwandan government has supported young women and men in accessing credit with the aim that young people may improve their entrepreneurial capabilities; grow their firms, and continuously contribute to the Rwandan economy (Anyanwu, 2013). Therefore, this current study strived to provide detailed information by scrutinizing the contribution of entrepreneurial credit accessibility to the growth of youth-owned MSEs. The following hypotheses were built on the conceptual framework:

Ho2: Credit accessibility has no significant contribution to the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Rwanda.

2.2.3 Online Social Media and Growth of Youth-Owned MSEs

Various studies have indicated that online technology-based online social media improve business process and growth, (Winer, 2009). Some scholars have confirmed that the utilization of online social media increased interaction with customers, and sales return, and it has been found that there is a positive correlation between online social media and the growth of youth-owned MSEs, (Rapp *et al*, 2013). Handayani and Mahendrawathi (2019) revealed that the use of online social media influences the social capital of any business organization, which increases its financial and non-financial growth. Kemi (2016) demonstrated that the use of Facebook, LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube, and Whatsapp had positively boosted sales growth. The study also noted that firms adopted these social media for product promotion, advertising services delivery, and showing different brands held by the enterprise. Xiang and Gretzel 2010; Parveen, Jaafar, and Ainin, (2015) explored how social media adoption influences the performance of small business companies and noted online social media increases sales turnover and the growth of SMEs. Many researchers noted that firms with the use of online social media performed well in their business activities than firms that were not concentrated on that (Appel *et al*, 2020).

According to Malthouse *et al*, (2013), online social media allows MSEs to access regional and international markets as some products are sold through social media. They further confirmed that online social media has removed geographical boundaries that were market entrance restrictions for MSEs. On the other hand, in developing countries MSEs ignore online social media because people depend on cultures of face-to-face bargaining instead of bargaining via online social media (Vij & James, 2014). Online social media entails incorporating new technological approaches that a firm uses to enter the market and improve growth through interacting with and reaching customers (Wang, & Kim, 2017). Malthouse *et al*, (2013) confirmed that online social media enables MSEs to enter the market without geographical boundaries. Another study by Rapp *et al*, (2013) noted that firms with the utilization of online social media can achieve growth as a result of reaching customers and finally making more sales. Hence, this current study strived to provide updated data by examining the contribution of technology-based online social media to the growth of youth-owned MSEs. The following hypotheses were formulated based on the conceptual framework:

Ho3: Online social media adoption has no significant contribution to the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Rwanda.

2.2.4 Market Access and Growth of Youth-Owned MSEs

Market access influences on the growth of enterprises since market accessibility increases the probability of growth achievement through making more sales (Hessels, & van, 2011). Therefore, market access has been noted as an essential factor affecting the growth of MSEs. According to Seelos and Mair (2007), youth-owned MSEs with more market information and other market facilities can realize firm growth. It has been asserted that MSEs' growth is determined by how an enterprise accesses market opportunities for maximizing its output. Chigunta (2001) scrutinized the issues limited small business organizations to access local and international markets. The study found that MSEs do not have enough skills for innovating their product and services which limit their competitiveness in international markets. Empirical evidence asserted that youth-owned enterprises copied and operated successful businesses which lead to high local competition.

Ali *et al*, (2020) investigated the obstacles and public policies encumbering small enterprises' international market expansion in Sub-Saharan Countries. The study used access procurement access, contracts access, financing regulatory structure, and access to market information as independent variables. The findings indicated that market information barriers and institutional environment have negative influences on the expansion of small business organizations and these barriers reduce their accessibility to the regional and international markets. Chigunta (2001) scrutinized the issues limited small business organizations to access international markets. This is because youths do not have enough skills about innovating their product and services which limit their competitiveness in global markets. For that reason, this current study endeavored to provide current information by examining the contribution of entrepreneurial training to the growth of youth-owned MSEs. The following hypotheses were built on the conceptual framework:

Ho4: Market access has no significant contribution to the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Rwanda.

3. Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

Explanatory and descriptive research designs were adopted in this research. Descriptive research design has vital in delineating the nature of the relationship between dependent and independent variables, (Muathe, 2010, Rahi, 2017). An explanatory research design determines the causal relationship between government entrepreneurial interventions and the growth of youth-owned MSEs, (Mathie, 2006).

3.2 Study Context and Population

The study was carried out in 35 administrative sectors comprising Gasabo, Kicukiro, and Nyarugenge which are three districts of Kigali city, Rwanda. The City of Kigali was selected because of the highest number of youth-owned MSEs benefiting entrepreneurial interventions delivered by the government. Some youth-owned MSEs strived to bring their enterprise to success while others failed thus being appropriate for this study. The study has chosen MSEs since they occupied more than 90% of youth and MSEs have been found to generate income and employment opportunities for a high proportion of inhabitants.

The study also concentrated on the youth-owned MSEs; with 35 years and below and who were operating economic activities in the City of Kigali for the period of data collection. The study also targeted youth-owned MSEs that got at least one entrepreneurial intervention given by the government. The MSEs were drawn from the following different business sectors, agriculture, mining, commerce, services, manufacturing, and energy. For the youth-owned Micro and Small Enterprises being unit of population, they ought to operate a profitable business as well as hold a recent business certificate. The unit of analysis was the MSEs, while the unit of observation was the youth-managed MSEs. The stratified sampling technique was also employed to select 154 youth-owned MSEs from 252 of the population (Alene, 2020). The Yamane (1967) formula was utilized to formulate a sample size. The study gathered data using open and closed-ended questions to assess the effect of government entrepreneurial interventions on the growth of MSEs in Kigali city, Rwanda.

3.3 Research Data and Analysis

The questionnaires were used to collect data from youth-owned MSEs related to the government entrepreneurial interventions and growth of youth-owned MSEs. The data which was mainly quantitative in nature was analyzed using multiple linear regression. However, before the analysis diagnostic tests were carried on to test the assumption of regression analysis.

4. Results and Discussion

The study intended to test whether government entrepreneurial interventions have an impact on the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Kigali Rwanda.

4.1 Regression Analysis

As good practice before the regression analysis which was used to test the hypotheses of the study was done it was necessary to test the assumption of the regression. The results are presented below

4.2 Diagnostic tests

Several diagnostic tests were undertaken to confirm whether the basic assumptions of the regression model has not been violated and the findings were presented below

Table1: Diagnostic tests

Test	Measures	Results	Interpretations
Multicollinearity	VIF	VIF>10	No multicollinearity

Normality	Shapiro-wilk test	P>0.05	Normally distributed
Sample adequacy	Bartlett's Test of Sphericity and Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	KMO 0.806 Bartlett's Test 0.000	The research sample was adequate
Linearity	Pearson's correlation coefficient	r > 0	Positive linear relationship
Reliability	Entrepreneurial training	0.857	Reliable
	Access to credit	0.889	Reliable
	Online social media	0.900	Reliable
	Market access	0.875	Reliable
	Individual characteristics	0.919	Reliable
	Growth	0.797	Reliable

The sample adequacy, linearity, homoscedasticity, normality, and multicollinearity assumptions of the linear regression model have been examined and analyzed to confirm the specification of the linear regression model (Morgan *et al*, 2019)

4.3.1 Testing of Hypotheses

H₀₁: Entrepreneurial training does not influence the growth of MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda.

H₀₂: Access to credit does not contribute to the growth of MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda.

H₀₃: Online social media does not contribute to the growth of MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda.

H₀₄: Market access does not contribute to the growth of MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda.

4.3.1 Model Summary

The adjusted R squared indicates the variation in the MSEs' growth caused by equal changes in the government entrepreneurial interventions as displayed by results in table 2.

Table 2: Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. the Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Durbin Watson
1	.791 ^a	.626	.616	.17001	.626	2.767

Table 2, shows the adjusted R-squared value of 0.626. It indicated that there is a variation of 62% in the growth of SMEs in Kigali city due to training, access to credit, online social media, and market access, and it has been measured using a 95% of confidence level. The study shows that all other factors remain constant; the 62% change in the growth of MSEs is contributed by variations in entrepreneurial training, access to credit, online social media, and market access. Table 2 indicated the strong correlation between government entrepreneurial interventions and the growth of MSEs as indicated by a robust coefficient of correlation of 0.791.

4.3.2 Analysis of Variance (ANOVA)

The significance of the study was also tested by use of the ANOVA method and the results were displayed in Table 3 below.

Table 3: ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	7.221	4	1.805	62.454	.000 ^b
	Residual	4.307	149	.029		
	Total	11.527	153			

a. Dependent Variable: growth

b. Predictors: (Constant), training, credit, online social media, market access

Table 3 indicates that the p-value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 and $F(4,149) = 62.454$. This is an indication that entrepreneurial training, access to credit, online social media, and market access has a significant contribution to the MSEs' growth in Kigali city, Rwanda.

Table 4: Regression Coefficient

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.607	.499		1.217	.024
	Entrepreneurial Training	.171	.117	.161	1.466	.016
	Access to credit	.109	.111	.112	.981	.032
	Online Social Media	.111	.135	.106	.825	.042
	Access to Market	.764	.144	.697	5.315	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Growth of youth-owned MSEs

Source: Survey data, 2022

Table 4 shows that entrepreneurial training, access to credit, online social media, and market access are individually correlated with the growth of youth-owned MSEs. The following model has been drawn from table 4:

Growth of MSEs = 0.607 + 0.171 entrepreneurial training + 0.109 access to credit + 0.111online social media + 0.764 access to market + e.....Model 1

H₀₁: Entrepreneurial training does not affect the MSEs' growth in Kigali, Rwanda.

Table 4 shows that entrepreneurial training and the growth of MSEs specifically those managed by youth; the two variables are statistically correlated as $\beta = 0.171$ and $p = 0.016$ which is less than 0.05 at the confidence level of 95%. **H₀₁** was rejected; it means that entrepreneurial training affected the MSEs' growth in Kigali. The results found in Table 4.5 do not differ from the resource-based view and other studies. According to the Resource-Based View, access to the resources such as training is critical for firms to achieve growth (Brem & Wolfram 2014). These arguments are agreed with studies by Haider, *et al*, (2017), and Mamo, (2022), who found that entrepreneurial training, is the main component of government entrepreneurial interventions that allow firms to access knowledge-based needed for the growth of enterprises. Other studies, including that by Semegn and Bishno, (2021), which reflected on the influence of training on the growth of the firm in Ethiopia, they agreed with the findings of this study; since their studies confirmed training as an important factor that contributes to the growth of enterprises.

H₀₂: Access to credit does not affect the MSEs' growth in Kigali, Rwanda.

Table 4.5 shows that access to credit has $\beta = 0.109$ and $p = 0.032$ which is less than 0.05. Access to credit has an effect on the growth of micro and small enterprises in Kigali, Rwanda, according to a 95 percent confidence level. It is indicated that there is a substantial correlation between access to credit and the growth of MSEs in Kigali,

Rwanda, at a confidence level of 95%. H_{02} was rejected. The findings agreed with other research carried out by Semegn and Bishno, (2021), which was dedicated to the effect of credit on firm growth in Nigeria, they are agreed with the findings of this study; since their studies confirmed that finances accessibility has a substantial impact on the growth of enterprises, additionally, Acquah and Mensah's (2015) study noted that financial credit contributes to firm growth. RBV theory arguments support these findings because credit enables enterprises to access other existing resources needed for firm growth (Sok, O'Cass, & Sok, 2013).

H_{03} : Online social media does not influence the MSEs' growth in Kigali, Rwanda.

Table 4 reveals that online social media has an important contribution to the growth of MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda, with $p=0.042$ being less than 0.05. It means that H_{03} was rejected, and it means that the alternative hypothesis was accepted. Online social media has the greatest impact on customer retention and sales improvement. According to the study by Salim and Sulaiman (2011), online social media and growth are statistically and positively correlated even if; some enterprises do not focus on online social media. Moreover, Sylvie (2012) found that online social media positively influence the growth of small firms.

H_{04} : Market access does not influence the growth of MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda.

The study reveals that there is a positive correlation between market access and growth of MSEs in Kigali, Rwanda at a confidence level of 95%, as $\beta= 0.764$ and $p=0.000$ lesser than 0.05. H_{04} was rejected and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. Different studies revealed a positive relationship between market access and growth (Al-Ansari, Pervan, and Xu, 2013). Therefore, access to market enables firms to sell more as well as to grow. Different forms of accessing resources are unique approaches that youth-owned MSEs utilize to create possibilities in a changing economy (Schumpeter, 1942).

5. Conclusion and Policy Recommendation

5.1 Conclusion

The purpose of the study was to investigate the effect of government entrepreneurial interventions on the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Kigali City, Rwanda. The study concluded that the growth of MSEs has been based on the resources-based view, Gibb's support, technology-based online social media adoption, and the growth of firm theories. Government entrepreneurial interventions enabled MSEs to survive and grow from the infancy to the maturity stage. The research findings confirmed that the four components of the government entrepreneurial interventions have significantly influenced the growth of youth-owned MSEs. The level of growth explained has been attributed to resource accessibility. Many empirical studies agreed with this research that financial credit is the most cogent for the growth of any enterprise.

5.2 Policy Implication

Entrepreneurial training had a positive effect on the growth of youth-owned MSEs in Kigali city, Rwanda hence Government through the relevant ministry should enhance training to the growth. The entrepreneurial training should be given to the MSEs and their employees so that they can gain necessary skills in various aspects of managing the business, the course of entrepreneurship should be included curriculum at all levels. This will have an overall positive influence on the sustainability of their business. The Rwandan government and its stakeholders should intervene by designing and enforcing a financial strategy to assist the MSEs to get credit in flexible terms. The study recommends that the government and its partners must create platforms aimed at providing market information to the MSEs. The study highly recommended that micro and small business use technology-based online social media in business operations as a better way to reach and, or interact with customers during this period of online business.

5.3 Limitation and Future direction of Research

The authors note that there are several limitations to the findings of the study. The data was obtained from self-reported data by the respondents and could have challenges of accuracy particularly on the growth construct of the study. Hence for validation purposes, future research could design a similar study with an expanded scope of respondents to include the public players. Secondly, the conceptual scope of the operationalization of the independent variable was limited by the four components of government entrepreneurial interventions. It is therefore suggested that future research could expand the set of components investigated under the component of government entrepreneurial interventions.

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